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Extension and Validation of Minimalistic Prediction Model to Determine the Energy Production of Offshore Wind Farms

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Abstract. Calculations of annual energy productions of wind farms are normally very computing demanding as they require simulations of the wind flow field inside the wind farms for a range of ambient wind conditions and directions. Although there exists many advanced computing tools for atmospheric flows, which, in principle, cope with all flow situations, most wind power developers rely their work on simplified engineering models based on analytical approaches and superposition of the flow behind a single row of wind turbines. An alternative to wake modeling is the fully developed wind farm array boundary layer model, which assumes that the wind farm is so large, that the wind field inside the wind farm is in equilibrium with the flow field of the ambient atmospheric boundary layer. Such a model was recently further developed by the authors using a simple correction for coping with finite-sized wind farms. The purpose of the present work is to extend further the finiteness correction formula and validate the model by comparing results to actual production data and to results from other simulation models, such as the Jensen, Gaussian and TurbOPark engineering models. In spite of the simplicity of the proposed model, it outperforms the other models, achieving results within 5% accuracy as compared with full-scale data from existing wind farms.

1. Introduction

To assess and design energy efficient wind farms it is required to compute the annual energy production using a numerical tool for determining wake losses and blockage. Calculations of annual energy productions are normally very computing demanding as they require simulations of the wind flow field inside the wind farms for a range of ambient wind speeds and directions covering the local statistics of the wind climate. Although there exists a lot of advanced computing tools for atmospheric flows that solve the full field equations, which, in principle, may cope with all flow situations, they are challenged by realistic boundary conditions and prohibitive computing costs. As a consequence, most wind power developers rely their work on simplified engineering models based on analytical wake deficit approaches and establish the required wind farm flow field by superposition of the flow behind individual wind turbines. The wake models cover a large range of techniques of varying complexity, ranging from

simplified engineering models, such as the now classical Jensen model [1] and the Gaussian model of Bastankhah and Porté-Agel [2], to linearized Navier-Stokes based solvers, such as Fuga [3], and to Navier-Stokes based approaches, such as Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) [4] and Large Eddy Simulation (LES) models [5]. An alternative to the wake models is the fully developed wind farm array boundary layer model, which was originally developed by Templin [6] and Frandsen [7]. This model assumes that the wind farm is so large, that the wind field inside the wind farm is in equilibrium with the flow field of the ambient atmospheric boundary layer, resulting in a simple analytical expression for the homogeneous average equilibrium velocity within the wind farm. This model has recently been extended with a simple correction for coping with finite-sized wind farms and the turbine inflow non-homogeneities following from this [8]. The modified flow model was subsequently utilized in combination with a cost model to determine the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCoE) for wind farms [8]. In spite of the simplicity of the model, model results showed a surprisingly good agreement with full-scale data from existing wind farms.

The purpose of the present work is to refine and validate the correction formula developed in [8] further by comparing results to actual production data and to results from other models. In the following, the model is referred to as the minimalistic model. In the paper, we show the details of the refined model and compare results from the minimalistic model with other more advanced prediction models and actual production data.

2. Modelling and methods

In this section, we give a brief overview of the models employed in the present work. As a backbone for the computations we use *PyWake* [9], which is the DTU open-source wind farm simulation tool used for studying the flow interaction between turbines within a wind farm, as well as the influence of the wakes on power production. *PyWake* provides a unified interface to wind farm models of different fidelities, including a range of engineering models, the linearized CFD-RANS model *Fuga* [3], as well as conventional CFD-RANS. In the present work, *Fuga* is used to determine the correction factor for ‘finiteness’ of wind farms in the simplistic model. The models used for the comparison are the N.O. Jensen (NOJ) wake model [1], the Gaussian deficit model by Bastankhah and Porté-Agel (BGD) [2], and the *TurbOPark* model developed by Ørsted [10]. All the models are implemented in *PyWake* [9]. To determine annual power productions the models are combined with wind direction distributions and conditional wind speed statistics based on Weibull distributions, with the two Weibull parameters tabulated as a function of wind direction. If not ‘standard’ wake expansion factors are used, additional input in terms of turbulence intensity – ultimately conditioned on wind direction – is required, and guidance for estimation of site specific expansion factors can be found in [18]. In the following we give a brief overview of the different models used in the study.

2.1. The minimalistic model

The basis of the minimalistic model is the assumption that the flow inside the wind farm is in equilibrium with the surrounding flow, corresponding to the wake effects being the same everywhere within the wind farm. This presumption, in turn, results in a simple analytical expression for the homogeneous average equilibrium velocity within the wind farm ([6], [7]). As shown in [8], this limits the input parameters to an absolute minimum, hence wind turbine data are only diameter and nameplate capacity, wind farm data are restricted to the area of the wind farm and number of wind turbines, and site data are restricted to average or sector-wise Weibull parameters. The assumption of equilibrium limits in principle the capability of the model to very large wind farms [7]. However, in [8] a simple technique for introducing the ‘finiteness’ of a wind farm was given as a simple correction equation for the wind farm power production,

$$P_E = (N_T - a\sqrt{N_T})P_{WF} + a\sqrt{N_T}P_{free} \quad , \quad (1)$$

where N_T is the number of wind turbines in the wind farm, P_E is the resulting computed wind power production, P_{WF} is the power production of a wind turbine inside the wind farm, and P_{free} is the production of a freely operating wind turbine without wake effects impinging from upstream turbines. Here a is a correction constant that ideally should be calibrated against performance data from actual wind farms or computational high-fidelity results from e.g. Navier-Stokes simulations. In the previous work a value $a=3$ was employed. Assuming a quadratic wind farm layout, this corresponds to stating that the average number of wind turbines subject to freestream conditions corresponds to 3/4 of the turbines located along the outer edges of the wind farm. It should be emphasized that the a -value is simple way of describing that a part of the wind turbines in a wind farm always will be subject to freestream conditions. Hence, depending on the topology of the wind farm and the wind statistics, the a -value may in principle take values as large as $\sqrt{N_T}$. It is clear that the value depends on wind farm topology, number of turbines, wind turbine interspacing, and turbulence intensity. The main motivation for the present work is to assess the robustness of the used a -value and, if needed, to derive a parameter-dependent expression for the a -value. It should be noted though, that the constant value used in [8] actually predicted results within 10% as compared to actual production data, which is indeed comparable with the performance of more detailed models.

2.2 Refined minimalistic model: calibration of the a -parameter

To determine more precisely the a -parameter, we use the *Fuga* wind farm model [3] (see below). This is done by defining an ‘infinite’ reference wind farm consisting of a large number of wind turbines arranged in a square, and then employ *Fuga* to compute the annual average power for different subsets of the farm, using the number of turbines, the average distance between the turbines and the average wind speed as input parameters. As reference conditions, we employ the wind characteristics at Horns Rev 1 and V80-2MV wind turbines. By rearranging eq. (1), the a -parameter can be determined as

$$a(N_T, U, S) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_T}} \frac{P(N_T, U, S) - N_T P_{inf}(U, S)}{P_{free}(U) - P_{inf}(U, S)}, \quad (2)$$

where P_{inf} is the reference power production of a wind turbine operating in the middle of the ‘infinite’ wind farm and P is the actual computed power production. Please note that P in this formulation differs from P_E defined in eq. (1), as P_E represents the annual wind farm production incorporating convolution with the mean wind speed Weibull distribution, whereas the value in eq. (2) represents the production at wind speed U . Carrying out a series of runs defined by varying the number of turbines, N_T , the mean wind speed, U , and the distance in diameters between the turbines, S , the output parameter $a = a(N_T, U, S)$ is parametrized in a data base and fitted to hyper-planes using polynomial regression, from which a -values from actual wind farms subsequently can be determined by interpolation.

2.2.1 Methodology. The method used to determine the a -parameter employing *Fuga* involves the following steps (see [11] for more details):

- Define the layout of wind turbines and the sector of wind direction. The layout comprises a square arrangement of $\sqrt{N_T} \times \sqrt{N_T}$ wind turbines formed as a matrix with perpendicular rows/columns with equal spacing (see Fig. 1). Due to symmetry, only a 45° inflow sector of the wind farm is considered, with a directional resolution of 1°. Hence, for any given

combination of the parameters (N_T, U, S) the mean production is determined as an average of the 45 inflow directions.

- Determine the mean production of a cluster of wind turbines, assuming the wake is in equilibrium with the atmospheric boundary layer within an "infinite" wind farm consisting of 50×50 turbines (i.e. $N_T = 2500$). The considered cluster consists of 5×5 wind turbines located so deep inside the wind farm, as seen from the inflow wind direction, that the power production of it can be assumed to be in equilibrium with the ambient flow. The power production of this reference wind farm cluster we refer to as P_{inf} (see eq. 2) and is expected only to depend on the mean wind speed, U , and the wind turbine interspacing, S .
- Compute the production of a single wind turbine operating independently in the free wind using the wind turbine power curve. This production is denoted as P_{free} and depends only on the inflow velocity, U .
- Compute the power production $P(N_T, U, S)$ from finite wind farms with turbine layout similar to the "infinite" wind farm for a range of ambient mean wind speeds within the operating wind speed regime of the wind turbines and a range of wind turbine spacing. The input parameters used here are:

$$n = [5, 10, \dots, 45], \text{ with } n = \sqrt{N_T}$$

$$U = [5, 6, \dots, 25] \text{ m/s}$$

$$S = [3, 4, \dots, 12]$$

Fig. 1. Plots illustrating the set-up for determining the a -value using *Fuga*. Left: Fictitious wind farm for the calculation of P_{inf} with AEP computed for $U = 9$ and $S = 7$. Right: Wind rose showing the direction sector used for the calculations.

Figure 1 shows the matrix structure of the reference wind farm used to determine the reference power production deep inside the wind farm, P_{inf} . For the purpose of illustration, the outcome of a computation of the Annual Energy Production (AEP) is shown for all wind turbines in the wind farm. The colors refer to the production of the individual wind turbines. For wind speeds significantly higher than the rated one, the power production becomes constant equal to the maximum achievable one, as the power

production has reached the nameplate capacity for all turbines, and all wind turbines in the farm thus produce a power corresponding to a freely operating wind turbine. This is shown in Fig. 2, which shows the annual power production per wind turbine as function of spacing and mean wind speed. Here, it is seen that for the considered cases, the power production becomes constant for mean wind speeds between 15 and 20 m/s, depending on the interspacing of the turbines.

Fig. 2. Annual energy production (per wind turbine) for 5 x 5 wind farm subject to fully developed wake flow as a function of mean wind speed (left) and interspacing (right).

2.2.2 Parameter results. Based on the above described procedure a database is created, using polynomial regression, with the parameters (N_T, U, S) as input and the a -parameter as output. An example of the results are shown in Fig. 3, which depicts iso-surface plots of the a -parameter as function of spacing, S , number of edge turbines, $\sqrt{N_T}$, and inflow wind speed, U .

Fig. 3. Examples of iso-surface plots of the computed a -value as function of spacing, number of wind turbines and wind speed. Left: Wind speed, $U = 8$ m/s; Right: Spacing $S = 7$.

From the analysis, there are several observations. For a fixed wind speed, the coefficient initially increases with the wind turbine spacing, S , until it reaches a value of 5-6, after which it starts to decrease (Fig. 3 (left)). Increasing the wind speed above the rated will tend to increase a further, as seen in Fig. 3 (right). For very high wind speeds, however, the a -value becomes meaningless, as the turbines in the

wake will generate a power production corresponding to the name plate capacity, hence $P_{free} = P_{inf}$ (see Fig. 2) and a can in principle take any value. What is more interesting is which a -value will be obtained for the average wind speed acting on an actual wind farm. As examples, we have here chosen the Lillgrund, the two Rødsand and the three Horns Rev wind farms. The data for the wind farms are given in Table 1, which shows the number of wind turbines, N_T , the rotor diameter of each turbine, D , the area of the wind farms, A , the Weibull parameters, (λ, k) mean wind speed at a height of 100 m, U , and the average normalized distance between the turbines, S . The mean distance between the wind turbines is determined using the formula (see [8] and [11])

$$S = \frac{1}{D} \frac{\sqrt{A}}{(\sqrt{N_T} - 1)}, \quad (3)$$

where the area is determined from the convex hull connecting the turbines located along the outer side of the wind farm [11]. Using these data as input to the data base, we get the a -values shown in the last column in the Table 1 (denoted a_{Fuga}). It is here seen that the a -parameters determined by *Fuga* vary between 4.1 to 5.9, depending on the wind farm. These values are clearly higher than the value of 3 used in the original model. However, the value in the original model took into consideration all losses, whereas the one from *Fuga* only deals with wake losses. Therefore, the power production achieved by *Fuga* and the other models used for comparison need to be corrected for additional losses when comparing the computations to actual production data. This will be discussed further in the following subsection.

Table 1: Wind farm data and computed averaged a -parameters using *Fuga*

Site	N_T [-]	n [-]	D [m]	A [km ²]	λ [m/s]	k [-]	U [m/s]	S [-]	a_{Fuga} [-]
Lillgrund	48	6.9	93	4.7	9.7	2.4	8.6	3.9	4.1
Rødsand 1	72	8.5	82	23.4	10.5	2.4	9.3	7.9	5.4
Rødsand 2	90	9.5	93	34.8	10.5	2.4	9.3	7.5	5.8
Horns Rev 1	80	8.9	80	19.6	11	2.4	9.8	7.0	5.7
Horns Rev 2	91	9.5	93	35.8	11.2	2.4	9.9	7.5	5.9
Horns Rev 3	49	7.0	164	100.7	11.5	2.4	10.2	10.2	4.8

2.2.3 Wind farm power losses. In order to accurately compute the real production of a wind farm, it is necessary to consider not only wake losses but also other energy losses that occur in all wind farms. In the original model [8], the a -parameter essentially accounted for all losses. However, in reality, and in particular when validating model results against actual production data, it is important to distinguish between wake losses and other losses. As discussed by Cabioch [12] and Gylling [13], other losses originate from electrical components and grid at the point of common coupling (electrical losses), the characteristics of the wind turbine rotor (turbine effectiveness), and the availability of the wind turbines (due to component breakdown and wear). Gylling [13] provides a range of typical values for these factors, while Cabioch [12] presents typical values specifically for British offshore wind farms. Combining the results from both sources, additional losses can be estimated to be about 4% related to the electrical and turbine performance and about 5% to loss of availability. The loss of availability is here only related to component failures and wear and tear, and does not include curtailment. If otherwise the availability is unknown, the total additional losses are about 9%, resulting in an additional loss factor, $\eta_{loss} = 0.91$, that needs to be multiplied with the computed power production in order to validate this

against actual production data. Hence, an additional loss factor needs to be considered in order to compute the actual power production calibrated with the *Fuga* wake model.

$$P_{E,Fuga} = \eta_{loss} \left[(N_T - a_{Fuga} \sqrt{N_T}) P_{WF} + a_{Fuga} \sqrt{N_T} P_{free} \right]. \quad (4)$$

It is of course also interesting to assess the relation between the original a -value and the value computed by *Fuga*. This relationship can be determined equating the power production in eq. (1) with the one in eq. (4),

$$(N_T - a \sqrt{N_T}) P_{WF} + a \sqrt{N_T} P_{free} = \eta_{loss} \left[(N_T - a_{Fuga} \sqrt{N_T}) P_{WF} + a_{Fuga} \sqrt{N_T} P_{free} \right]. \quad (5)$$

Rearranging the terms, we get

$$a_{Fuga} = \frac{1}{\eta_{loss}} \left[a + \sqrt{N_T} (1 - \eta_{loss}) \frac{P_{WF}}{P_{free} - P_{WF}} \right]. \quad (6)$$

Inserting $a = 3$ and $\eta_{loss} = 0.91$, as well as values for the computed power production and the number of wind turbines, the equivalent a_{Fuga} -value is determined for the tested wind farms. Here the a_{Fuga} -values range from 3.5 (Lillgrund) to 4.2 (Horns Rev 3), with most values being around 4.0. This is still less than the values shown in Table 1, but, as will be shown later when comparing to actual production data, it also illustrates the influence of using different a -values.

2.3 Other prediction models

In the following we briefly introduce to the prediction models used for comparison. For more details about the models we refer to the documentation in *PyWake* [9]. It should be noted that for all models the computed production is multiplied by a loss factor $\eta_{loss} = 0.91$.

2.3.1 The N.O. Jensen wake model. This model is the oldest and simplest wake model [1]. Assuming a top-hat velocity deficit, it combines one-dimensional momentum theory with the assumption of a linear expansion of the wake, resulting in a simple analytical equations for velocity deficit. The model further includes a simple technique for determining the deficit for multiple wakes using a squared sum superposition. The only unknown parameter of the model is the expansion coefficient, which essentially depends on the turbulence intensity. In the present work, we employ a wake expansion factor $k = 0.32$, which using the Niayifar formula [14], corresponds to 7.5% free-stream turbulence intensity. It should be noted that using more advanced formulations of the Jensen model, using e.g. local turbulence intensity and wind speeds, did not change the results noticeable.

2.3.2 The Gaussian deficit model. This model is based mass and momentum conservation combined with the assumption of a self-similar Gaussian profile for the wake deficit. Like in the case of the N.O. Jensen model, this results in a general expression for the velocity deficit in which the wake expansion is a function of the local turbulence intensity. The used model includes a Gaussian overlap, and an average local wind speed at the rotor plane. For more details, we refer to the TurbOPark documentation [15].

2.3.3 TurbOPark. This model follows the basics of the Gaussian deficit model with a wake expansion that is locally linear and an expansion rate determined by the local turbulence intensity in the wake. Furthermore, it also includes expressions for wind blockage. The model is developed by Ørsted and has been calibrated to match the production of Ørsted's portfolio of wind farms [15]. As for all the models

used in the present work, the predicted power production is multiplied by η_{loss} , even though some of the loss probably already is included in the calibration.

2.3.4 Fuga. Fuga is based on superposition of solutions to the linearized turbulent Navier-Stokes equations with the rotors in the wind farm represented by actuator discs and the Reynolds stresses represented by a ‘simple’ eddy viscosity type of closure with the prescribed eddy viscosity $K = \kappa u_* z$, where κ denotes the von Karman constant, u_* is the friction velocity, and z is the height above terrain. This simple closure works surprisingly well for wakes; actually, better than standard $k-\epsilon$ and mixing length closures. The equations are formulated in a mixed spectral domain, which facilitates extremely fast solutions based on a ‘system’ of look-up tables, where some are general, and others are wind turbine specific. These tables are subsequently used to determine the velocity field behind a single solitary wind turbine. It was developed at Risø by Ott et al. [3] and is considered as one of the fastest full field models for wind farm computations. In the present work it is employed to determine refined values for the a -parameter in the simplistic model (see subsection 2.3).

3 Wind farm production data

To assess the improvements to the minimalistic model and to cross-validate against the other models we compare the model results to actual production data for the wind farms shown in Table 1. Except for the Lillgrund wind farm, where it has not been possible to get production data over time, we have access to production data for remaining five (Danish) wind farms through the Danish Energy Agency [16]. These are shown in Fig. 4, which depicts production data over time for the two Rødsand and the three Horns Rev wind farms. Most data exist for Horns Rev 1 and Rødsand 1, as both were put in production in 2003, whereas only data from 2018 exists for the Horns Rev 3 wind farm. Typically for all wind farms are that they in the first few years in operation produce less than in the following years due to start problems. Furthermore, mainly due to requests from German wind power producers, curtailment of the Danish wind power production started in 2019, hence production data from 2020 onwards should be avoided for validation, as the availability is unknown. Moreover, there is also a tendency that wind turbines will show an age-rated performance degradation due to a number of factors including component wear and tear. In Fig. 4 this is seen as a slight decrease in the mean slope of the production curves. We also observe changes from year to year that depends on changes in annual wind conditions.

Fig. 4. Evolution of the production of Danish offshore wind farms with values taken from the Danish Energy Agency [16].

Ignoring the first 2 years of operation and the years from 2020 onwards, we get the average annual production data for the validation by averaging the production for the remaining years. The result of this is given in Table 2. Based on the time histories of the production data of Rødsand 1 and 2, and of Horns Rev 1 and 2, we get a relative standard deviation between 6.7% and 17.0%, which is a measure of the variability of the annual wind conditions and of the degeneration of the wind farm performance that happens after some years in operation.

Table 2. Annual energy production and relative standard deviations for the considered wind farms.

	Lillgrund	Rødsand 1	Rødsand 2	HornsRev 1	HornsRev 2	HornsRev 3
AEP [GWh]	335	540	790	580	880	1750
RSD	N/A	9.6 %	6.8 %	17.0%	6.7 %	N/A

Unfortunately, we do not have access to the time series of the production data for the Lillgrund wind farm. However, in a work by Sebastiani et al. [17], SCADA data covering more than 2400 days of operation showed an average production of about 38 MW, including loss of availability, corresponding to an average AEP of 335 GWh per year.

4 Results and Discussion

In the following we compare the average annual production data for the wind farms given in Table 2 with results from the prediction models described in section 2. It is important to note that the Weibull parameters in Table 1 are averaged data. Since we have access to the frequency distributions of the Weibull parameters conditioned on wind direction, we divide the wind rose into twelve 30° sectors, and compute the AEP for each sector. The total annual energy production is subsequently determined by weighting the sector predictions with the frequency factor and summing them up to a total AEP. For each sector, this is done for both a free (solitary) wind turbine and a wind turbine in a fully developed wake flow, in order to obtain P_{free} and P_{WF} , respectively. The outcome of the computations is summarized in the bar charts of Fig. 5, which compares the computed AEP with the actual AEP, and in Fig. 6 which gives the relative percentage error between computed and measured production data. Furthermore, the mean absolute percentage error (*mape*) are for the different models given in Table 2.

Fig. 5. Comparison between computed and actual production of the different wind farms.

From the bar charts several observations can be made. First, except for the Gaussian model, all models predict an AEP within 10%, as compared to the actual (measured) AEP, which is considered as being very good. Moreover, we see that the original minimalistic model (referred to as Minimal-1) for all cases predicts an AEP with an deviation less than 7% and a *mape* of 4.9%, which is very close to the 4.1% achieved by *TurbOPark*. This is somewhat surprising as the parameters of *TurbOPark* model is

Table 3. Mean absolute percentage error (*mape*) in AEP for the various models.

Minimal-1	Minimal-2	N.O. Jensen	Gaussian	TurbOPark
4.9%	3.6%	5.2%	10.0%	4.1%

calibrated to fit with actual production data from nearly twenty existing wind farms. What is just as interesting is that the best performing model is the refined minimalistic model (Minimal-2), which, with a maximum deviation of about 6% and a *mape* of 3.6%, outperforms all the other models. It is not clear why the Gaussian model, with maximum deviation of about 18% and a *mape* of 10%, performs markedly worse than the other models.

Fig. 6. Relative error between measured and computed data for the different models.

5 Conclusions

The minimalistic wind farm energy prediction model by Sørensen and Larsen [8] was further developed to include a data base to determine the parameter correcting the ‘infinite’ wind farm assumption for ‘finiteness’. In the original model, a constant predefined correction parameter was used. In the present version of the model, this has been replaced by a look-up table based on *Fuga* computations of a generic wind farm. Input to the look-up table are the number of wind turbines, the wind speed, and the average distance between the turbines in the wind farm. The results demonstrate that, in spite of the simplistic nature of the model, the refined minimalistic model outperforms all the other employed models with respect to deliver accurate AEP predictions, hence achieving results with a maximum deviation of less than 6% for the wind farms considered. The other models that were employed for comparison are the original minimalistic model, the Jensen model, the Gaussian model, and the *TurbOPark* model.

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